

An efficient graph neural networks surrogate model for slope reliability analysis considering soil spatial variability

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Abstract

Soil spatial variability significantly affects slope stability and landslide behaviors, particularly under complex geological conditions where traditional finite element analysis (FEA), while precise, incurs prohibitive computational costs. This study introduces a new surrogate model leveraging graph attention networks (GAT) equipped with sample and aggregate (SAGE) sampling, designed to efficiently handle large-scale data while predicting slope safety factors and identifying potential slip surfaces. The GAT model utilizes a spatial graph construction based on k-dimensional trees (KD-Trees), enabling the effective representation of complex mechanical interactions within the soil. The results indicate superior performance of this model over traditional machine learning methods such as random forest, feedforward neural networks, support vector regression, and convolutional neural networks, achieving a mean squared error of 0.000218 and an R^2 of 0.995. The application of GAT with SAGE sampling highlights the potential of graph neural networks to significantly enhance real-time slope stability monitoring and risk assessment

in geotechnical engineering, demonstrating a promising direction for computationally efficient surrogate modeling.

Keywords: Geotechnical reliability; Graph attention networks (GAT); Soil spatial variability; Surrogate modeling; Computational geotechnics

List of Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
c	Cohesion	kPa
ϕ	Internal friction angle	°
γ	Unit weight	kN/m ³
FS	Safety factor	—
β	Reliability index	—
μ	Mean value	—
σ	Standard deviation	—
ρ	Correlation coefficient	—
θ	Correlation length	m
λ	Eigenvalue (KL expansion)	—
ξ	Standard normal variable	—
K	Covariance matrix	—
x, y	Spatial coordinates	m
d_{ij}	Euclidean distance between nodes	—
w_{ij}	Adjacency weight	—
α_{ij}	Attention weight (GAT)	—
h_i	Node feature vector	—
W	Learnable linear transformation	m

Introduction

To circumvent the prohibitive computational cost associated with direct Monte Carlo simulations coupled with finite element analysis (FEA) or other advanced numerical techniques for large-deformation landslide motion, granular collapse, or anisotropic rock mechanics, traditional surrogate models have been widely explored in geotechnical reliability analysis [1–3]. Techniques such as Kriging (or Gaussian process regression), response surface methods (RSM), and polynomial chaos expansion (PCE) serve as computationally inexpensive proxies by building an explicit mathematical approximation of the limit-state function [4]. These methods, often combined with advanced sampling strategies like Latin hypercube sampling or importance sampling, have proven effective for specific problems, as demonstrated by the work of Ding et al. [5] and Liu et al. [6] using Kriging-based approaches. However, the efficacy of these classical surrogates diminishes when confronted with the high-dimensional input spaces that inevitably arise from the discretization of random fields. This "curse of dimensionality," coupled with the strong nonlinearities inherent in soil mechanics, presents a significant barrier, limiting their accuracy and practical applicability in complex, large-scale geotechnical scenarios [7].

In response to the limitations of classical surrogates, researchers have increasingly turned to more flexible, general-purpose machine learning (ML) models [8]. Techniques such as feedforward neural networks (FNN), support vector regression (SVR), and ensemble methods like random forest (RF) and gradient boosting have shown powerful non-linear fitting capabilities [9,10,11]. These methods have been successfully applied to predict slope stability, often demonstrating superior performance over traditional deterministic

approaches [12]. In particular, deep neural networks (DNNs) have emerged as a powerful meta modeling technique for capturing complex, nonlinear dynamic responses in structural systems, such as high-rise buildings, and have been effectively used for fragility estimation [13]. Nevertheless, these standard ML models suffer from a fundamental and shared drawback: they are data-agnostic in structure and typically require input to be "flattened" into one-dimensional feature vectors. In the context of spatially variable soils, this means the two- or three-dimensional data representing the soil's properties are forcibly reshaped into a long vector. This process irrevocably destroys the physical spatial topology and neighborhood relationships among soil elements. Consequently, crucial information regarding stress transfer paths, material interfaces, and potential failure mechanisms is lost before the model even begins learning, fundamentally constraining its ability to capture the true physics of the problem [14,15].

To address this loss of spatial context, researchers intuitively turned to convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a class of deep learning models renowned for their ability to process grid-like data such as images. By converting the spatial distribution of soil properties from a random field or finite element analysis into an image-like format, several studies have successfully used CNNs and their variants (e.g., U-Net) to predict slope failure probabilities and failure surfaces [16,17]. This approach preserves spatial locality to some degree; however, it exposes the inherent limitation of CNNs: they are designed for and demand data on a regular, structured grid. This requirement is fundamentally incompatible with the unstructured, irregular finite element meshes that are standard practice in geotechnical engineering for accurately modeling complex slope geometries, material layers, and boundaries [18]. The mandatory process of interpolating or re-meshing an irregular FEM

output onto a regular grid is not only a source of significant computational overhead but also introduces geometric distortions and approximation errors, thereby undermining the very precision that a high-fidelity numerical model is meant to provide [19].

The respective limitations across all preceding methodologies, the high-dimensionality challenge for classical surrogates, the structure destroying nature of standard ML models, and the rigid grid-data requirements of CNNs, point compellingly towards a paradigm shift: graph neural networks (GNNs). GNNs are a class of deep learning methods specifically designed to operate on non-Euclidean data, with their defining advantage being the ability to work directly on arbitrarily structured graph data [20,21]. This makes them a native and powerful tool for geotechnical analysis. By mapping an irregular finite element mesh to a graph, where mesh elements become nodes and their adjacency defines the edges, GNNs can directly process the system's geometric and physical properties while preserving the complete topological information [19]. This approach allows the model to explicitly learn how stress, strain, and material properties propagate through the physically connected structure. The utility of GNNs for handling complex, mesh-based spatial problems is increasingly being recognized across diverse engineering disciplines, from predicting stress fields in complex mechanical structures [18] to modeling system-level risks in infrastructure networks [22,17]. Therefore, introducing GNNs to slope reliability analysis is not merely an incremental improvement but a logical and necessary evolution for addressing the fundamental limitations of existing methods. The main contributions of this study are summarized as follows:

(1) Methodological Innovation: This paper, for the first time, introduces a GNN framework for slope reliability analysis. By directly mapping irregular finite element meshes to graph structures, our approach fundamentally solves the problem faced by traditional ML models, where spatial data is "flattened," leading to an irreversible loss of physical interaction information. This innovation allows the model to learn directly on non-Euclidean data while preserving the full spatial topology and physical adjacencies of the geotechnical system.

(2) Proof of Performance Superiority: Through a systematic comparison with multiple benchmark models (including traditional ML and state-of-the-art CNNs) across three case studies of increasing complexity, this paper quantitatively demonstrates the superior accuracy and robustness of the GNN-based surrogate model in handling complex geological conditions, such as soil stratification and parameter cross-correlation. The results demonstrate that the GNN exhibits the lowest prediction error and highest stability in all tested scenarios.

(3) Practical Value and Efficiency Enhancement: This study confirms that the GNN surrogate model, while maintaining high predictive accuracy, significantly enhances computational efficiency, reducing finite element computation times from hours or even days to minutes in scale. This dramatic leap in efficiency provides a feasible tool for conducting large-scale Monte Carlo simulations (e.g., $>10^5$ samples) as well as for the analysis of low-probability failure events, offering a more powerful and practical instrument for risk assessment and reliability design in geotechnical engineering.

Methodology

2.1 General framework overview

This study proposes a GNN-based approach for efficient slope stability prediction, integrating spatial variability modeling with advanced ML techniques. The methodology follows a systematic pipeline that seamlessly combines data generation, graph construction, surrogate modeling, and reliability analysis to form a cohesive framework for slope stability assessment.

The framework begins with modeling the spatial variability of soil parameters using Gaussian random fields (GRF), which generate spatially correlated distributions for essential soil characteristics such as cohesion and friction angle. To address the computational challenges posed by high-dimensional random fields, the Karhunen–Loève (KL) expansion is applied for dimensionality reduction while preserving essential spatial correlations. This preprocessing step ensures that the generated data maintains realistic spatial dependencies while remaining computationally efficient for subsequent graph-based modeling.

Following data generation, finite element simulations provide spatial coordinates and soil mechanical properties, which serve as the foundational data for constructing the graph representation. Each soil element is represented as a node in the graph, with node features including spatial coordinates and mechanical properties. Using the KD-Tree method, adjacency relationships between nodes are established based on spatial proximity, with each node connected to its nearest neighbors. Edge weights are assigned based on Euclidean

distances, enabling the model to capture spatial dependencies and mechanical interactions effectively.

The core of the modeling process employs a graph attention network (GAT) architecture enhanced with sample and aggregate (GraphSAGE) sampling strategy. GAT utilizes multi-head attention mechanisms to dynamically weight the importance of node connections, allowing the model to focus on the most relevant spatial relationships within the soil structure. The GraphSAGE sampling approach efficiently samples and aggregates information from neighboring nodes, improving computational efficiency and enabling scalable learning from large graph structures. This combination leverages GAT's ability to capture complex spatial relationships and GraphSAGE's efficient neighborhood sampling, making it particularly suitable for handling large-scale geotechnical data with complex spatial dependencies [23].

Finally, reliability theory is integrated to account for uncertainties in soil parameters, while the strength reduction method (SRM) is used to calculate safety factors (SF) for slope stability analysis. These computed SFs serve as ground truth labels for the GNN model training and validation, creating a robust foundation for probabilistic slope stability assessment that accommodates both spatial variability and engineering uncertainties.

Overall, this methodological framework systematically integrates random field theory, graph-based machine learning, and geotechnical reliability analysis, forming a cohesive pipeline that addresses the computational limitations of traditional finite element analysis while maintaining high accuracy in capturing complex soil-structure interactions and spatial variability effects.

2.2 Cross-correlated random field discretization and dimensionality reduction

To accurately model the spatial variability and statistical interdependencies of multiple soil parameters, such as cohesion (c) and internal friction angle (ϕ), this study employs cross-correlated GRF. In geotechnical engineering, these parameters often exhibit statistical correlation from shared geological formation processes. This relationship is captured using a joint covariance matrix that defines both the spatial auto-covariance of each parameter and the cross-covariance between them.

To efficiently discretize these high-dimensional random fields for computational analysis, the Karhunen–Loeve (KL) expansion is applied. The primary advantage of the KL expansion is its capacity for optimal dimensionality reduction, which is essential to make large-scale reliability analysis computationally tractable. The joint KL expansion expresses the correlated random fields as a linear combination of orthogonal eigenfunctions weighted by independent standard normal variables:

$$H(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\mu}(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sqrt{\lambda_i} \boldsymbol{\psi}_i(\mathbf{x}) \xi_i \quad (1)$$

where $H(\mathbf{x})$ is the vector of random fields at spatial location \mathbf{x} , $\boldsymbol{\mu}(\mathbf{x})$ is the mean vector, λ_i and $\boldsymbol{\psi}_i(\mathbf{x})$ are the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of the joint covariance matrix, and ξ_i are independent standard normal variables.

By truncating the series and retaining only the leading terms corresponding to the largest eigenvalues, the KL expansion effectively compresses the random fields into a

manageable number of variables while preserving critical spatial information. This dimensionality reduction is crucial for the efficiency of the subsequent surrogate modeling process.

2.3 Data preparation and graph structure construction

2.3.1 Data source

The data used in this study is primarily derived from finite element simulations, which provide detailed soil characteristics essential for constructing the graph structure. These simulations model the spatial layout and mechanical properties of soil, including coordinates and parameters like cohesion and friction angle. For this study, two classic slope models were simulated: one representing an undrained soil slope and another that includes variations in cohesion and friction angle.

Finite element analysis (FEA) enables high-precision representation of spatial heterogeneity, ensuring that each soil element in the model accurately reflects real-world geological variability. This simulation-generated data serves as the foundation for creating a graph structure, where each soil element's spatial position and mechanical attributes are translated into graph nodes, ready for GNN processing.

2.3.2 Graph structure construction (KD-Tree adjacency and node feature definition)

Fig. 1 Comparison of mesh division and graph representation for slope stability analysis.

Fig. 1: The left side shows the finite element mesh used to capture soil spatial variability, while the right side illustrates the process of converting mesh elements into graph nodes and edges for the Graph Neural Network (GNN). This representation allows each mesh element's spatial data to be used as node features, enabling the GNN to model the spatial relationships among soil elements effectively [24].

To effectively represent spatial interactions within the soil model, a graph structure is constructed by using the KD-Tree algorithm. KD-Tree is an efficient spatial indexing method that organizes nodes based on their coordinates, allowing quick identification of neighboring nodes and establishing adjacency relationships. In this study, each soil element (or node) is connected to its ten nearest neighbors, forming a graph where edges represent spatial adjacency and convey critical interdependencies among soil elements.

In geotechnical finite element modeling, the choice of neighborhood size and type is key for both the physical interpretability and predictive performance of GNN models. The modified Saint-Venant principle suggests a mechanical interaction radius of about 20–40 m, much larger than the area covered by the ten nearest neighbors selected via the KD-Tree.

Typically, only 4–6 immediate neighbors have direct mechanical interaction, while the KD-Tree also includes spatially close but indirectly connected nodes.

Our experiments show that increasing neighbors from 4 to 10 yields only slight accuracy improvement, indicating that most spatial correlations are captured within a small neighborhood, and the 10-neighbor setting remains within the relevant physical range. The Graph Attention Network (GAT) further differentiates between direct and indirect neighbors using its attention mechanism: direct neighbors usually receive higher weights, dominating feature aggregation, while indirect neighbors provide supplementary spatial information without causing feature homogenization.

Given the spatial coordinates (x_i, y_i) of each node, the KD-Tree calculates the Euclidean distance between each node and its neighbors, defining edge weights that decrease with distance. Specifically, the weight w_{ij} between nodes i and j is determined by:

$$w_{ij} = \exp\left(-\frac{d_{ij}}{\alpha}\right) \quad (2)$$

where d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance between nodes i and j , and α is a scaling parameter that controls the influence of distance on edge strength. This Gaussian weighting function captures the gradual reduction in connection strength as nodes are farther apart, preserving spatial relationships essential for modeling soil variability.

Each graph node is characterized by features that include spatial coordinates (x, y) and soil mechanical properties such as cohesion and friction angle. These features directly reflect the spatial variability of the soil, allowing the GNN model to learn both location-

dependent and mechanical characteristics within the soil. By defining edges based on proximity, the graph structure effectively represents the spatial and mechanical interconnections, enabling the GNN to process soil data in a structured, spatially aware manner.

This data preparation and graph structure construction process ensures that the soil model is well-suited for GNN analysis. By combining finite element simulation data with KD-Tree-based graph construction, this approach maintains spatial accuracy and computational efficiency, providing a robust foundation for subsequent slope stability prediction.

2.4 Graph neural network modeling

2.4.1 GNN model design

The core of this study's slope stability prediction framework lies in the GNN model design, specifically leveraging the GraphSAGE strategy combined with a multi-head attention mechanism. GraphSAGE, or Graph Sample and Aggregate, is a neighborhood sampling and aggregation method that enables scalable learning on large graph structures by sampling a fixed number of neighboring nodes during each training iteration. This approach efficiently reduces memory usage and computational requirements while retaining essential neighborhood information, making it well-suited for large-scale geotechnical data with numerous soil elements [25].

In addition to GraphSAGE, a multi-head attention mechanism is incorporated to dynamically adjust the influence of neighboring nodes based on their importance, enhancing the model's representation capacity. Each node v updates its feature vector h_v by

aggregating information from its sampled neighbors using multiple attention heads, which independently process and weigh the contributions of each neighbor. This mechanism is especially valuable in capturing both local and global soil interactions, as it allows the model to focus more on critical nodes that have a significant impact on slope stability.

In GAT, each node i 's feature h_i is updated by aggregating information from its neighbors using the following attention mechanism:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\exp(\text{LeakyReLU}(a^T [W\mathbf{h}_i \parallel W\mathbf{h}_j]))}{\sum_{k \in N_i} \exp(\text{LeakyReLU}(a^T [W\mathbf{h}_i \parallel W\mathbf{h}_k]))} \quad (3)$$

where α_{ij} represents the attention weight between node i and neighbor j , h_i and h_j are the feature vectors of nodes i and j , W is a learnable linear transformation, and a is a parameter vector. This mechanism computes similarity scores, assigning greater importance to more relevant neighbors, which is essential for capturing local spatial relationships.

The multi-head attention mechanism further strengthens the model's ability to capture complex interactions. Multiple "attention heads" process different feature combinations, allowing the model to retain diverse layers of information. The multi-head update rule is as follows:

$$\mathbf{h}_{i'} = \parallel_{k=1}^K \sum_{j \in N_i} \alpha_{ij}^{(k)} W^{(k)} \mathbf{h}_j \quad (4)$$

where K is the number of attention heads, and \parallel represents concatenation. This approach enhances the model's capability to learn from high-dimensional features while maintaining computational efficiency.

2.4.2 Feature processing (Feature standardization and global feature aggregation)

To ensure consistent input data for the GNN model, feature processing steps include standardization and global feature aggregation. Feature standardization adjusts each node's features to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one, eliminating biases due to differing scales of input features like spatial coordinates and mechanical properties. This ensures that the model treats all features equitably, enhancing the stability and convergence speed during training.

After node-level feature extraction through multiple GNN layers, global feature aggregation is performed to create a unified representation of the entire slope graph. A mean pooling operation is then applied across all nodes to produce a single graph-level feature vector that captures the slope's overall spatial and mechanical characteristics. This global feature vector serves as the basis for the model's final prediction of the SF, providing a comprehensive assessment of slope stability.

2.4.3 Model training and optimization (Adam optimizer, learning rate scheduler, etc.)

The primary goal of model training is to minimize the error between the predicted values and the true values. To achieve precise and reliable safety factor predictions, this study utilizes Mean Squared Error (MSE) as the loss function, which calculates the average

squared difference between predicted and actual safety factors. The MSE formula is expressed as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

where y_i represents the actual safety factor, \hat{y}_i is the GNN model's predicted value, and n is the sample size. MSE serves as a key metric that guides the model in iteratively reducing prediction errors, enabling accurate safety factor estimation.

To accelerate training and improve optimization stability, the Adam optimizer is employed, a widely-used adaptive learning rate optimizer especially effective for managing complex gradient descent steps and handling sparse gradients. The Adam algorithm updates parameters using the following formula:

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t + \epsilon}} \hat{m}_t \quad (6)$$

where \hat{m}_t and \hat{v}_t are the first- and second-moment estimates, η is the learning rate, and ϵ is a small constant to prevent division by zero. By adapting the learning rate for each parameter individually, Adam enhances convergence speed and robustness, making it well-suited for complex graph structures.

In this study, the Leaky Rectified Linear Unit (LeakyReLU) activation function is employed. LeakyReLU is a variant of the traditional ReLU activation function, which allows a small, non-zero gradient when the input is negative. This helps to address the ‘‘dying ReLU’’ problem and enables the network to learn more effectively. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ \alpha x, & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where α is a small constant (typically 0.01) [26].

Given the inherent variability and potential imbalance in slope safety factors across different samples, data balancing techniques are applied during preprocessing. Oversampling and undersampling are combined to address the underrepresentation of certain safety factor ranges, ensuring a more uniform distribution of SF values. This approach enhances the model’s ability to generalize across the entire range of SF classes.

To maintain stable convergence, a StepLR learning rate scheduler is incorporated, which reduces the learning rate by a fixed factor after a specified number of epochs. StepLR’s simplicity and compatibility with iterative GNN training provides consistent, step-wise learning rate reductions that guide the model toward a well-optimized state. The initial higher learning rate promotes faster convergence in early stages, while gradual reduction refines optimization in later stages, ensuring efficient and stable training.

Finally, to further enhance model robustness and prevent overfitting, early stopping criteria are applied based on validation performance. This criterion monitors improvements in the validation MSE and halts training once improvements become negligible, thereby reducing unnecessary training iterations and enhancing model efficiency by ensuring the model trains only as long as necessary. Finally, to prevent overfitting and ensure adequate training, we implemented an early stopping strategy based on the validation loss. Specifically, the model training is halted if the validation loss does not improve by at least $1e-6$ for 10 consecutive epochs (patience = 10). The validation loss is monitored at the end

of each epoch, and the model parameters corresponding to the lowest validation loss are retained as the final model. This approach ensures that the model is neither undertrained nor overfitted.

2.4.4 Attention Mechanism Identification

The attention mechanism not only refines feature weights between nodes but also plays a critical role in identifying key nodes that significantly impact slope stability predictions. By learning attention weights for each node's interactions, the GNN model is able to determine which nodes contribute most to the final prediction. This process highlights nodes with higher mechanical properties, or nodes positioned in areas of potential instability, allowing for a more nuanced assessment of the factors influencing slope stability.

Key nodes are identified by examining attention weights, and visualizations, such as heatmaps, can be generated to show the distribution of these weights across the slope model. This interpretability feature provides valuable insights into which areas of the slope are most susceptible to failure, supporting proactive risk assessment and targeted interventions in slope management.

Through this combination of GraphSAGE sampling, multi-head attention, and robust feature processing, the GNN model is well-equipped to handle complex spatial relationships and high-dimensional geotechnical data, making it an effective tool for slope stability prediction.

Fig. 2 illustrates the overall architecture of the Graph Neural Network (GNN) model used for slope stability prediction. The model takes spatial data, including soil parameters

such as cohesion (c) and friction angle (φ), and converts it into a graph structure. Each node represents a soil element with features corresponding to its mechanical properties, and edges represent spatial relationships between nodes. The model processes these features through multiple graph attention layers (I, II, and III), where attention mechanisms dynamically adjust node interactions based on learned weights. The aggregated graph-level features are then passed through fully connected layers to predict the safety factor, offering a robust assessment of slope stability.

Fig. 2 Model architecture of the graph neural network for slope stability analysis.

2.5 Reliability Analysis and Slope Stability Calculation

In geotechnical engineering, soil parameters such as cohesion and friction angle exhibit inherent spatial variability and uncertainty due to natural heterogeneity. To account for these uncertainties in slope stability analysis, this study incorporates reliability theory, which provides a probabilistic framework for evaluating the likelihood of slope failure under varying soil conditions. By quantifying the uncertainty in key soil properties, reliability theory enables a more robust assessment of slope stability compared to deterministic approaches [27].

The integration of various sources of uncertainty, including both aleatory and epistemic types, is crucial for accurate risk assessment, and hybrid frameworks combining Bayesian methods with other probabilistic techniques have proven effective in this regard [28].

The reliability index β is used as a measure of slope stability, calculated based on the probability distribution of soil parameters. For this study, the reliability index is computed as follows:

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_R - \mu_S}{\sqrt{\sigma_R^2 + \sigma_S^2}} \quad (8)$$

where μ_R and μ_S are the mean values of soil shear strength and applied shear stress, respectively, and σ_R^2 and σ_S^2 are their variances. This reliability index β reflects the overall stability of the slope; a higher β indicates greater stability, while a lower β suggests increased failure risk. By incorporating spatial variability through probabilistic distributions, this approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of failure probability in response to uncertainties in soil properties.

Implementation Procedure

Fig. 3 Vertical workflow of GNN-Based slope stability analysis.

Fig. 3 illustrates the vertical workflow for GNN-based slope stability analysis. The workflow consists of seven key steps:

Step 1: Data Preparation

Define the slope geometry and statistical properties of soil parameters, such as layer thickness, slope angle, mean, coefficient of variation, and spatial autocorrelation. These inputs form the basis for subsequent modeling.

Step 2: Constructing the Random Field

Generate spatially correlated soil property distributions using Gaussian Random Fields and reduce dimensionality via Karhunen-Loève expansion to ensure computational efficiency.

Step 3: Graph Structure Generation

Build a graph where each node corresponds to a soil element. Use the KD-Tree method to identify the nearest neighbors and establish edges, capturing the mechanical relationships between elements.

Step 4: Finite Element Computation

Import the generated soil parameters into finite element software to compute safety factors. These results serve as ground truth labels for model training.

Step 5: Graph Neural Network Modeling

Design a GNN based on the Graph Attention Network (GAT) architecture, leveraging multi-head attention and GraphSAGE sampling to learn spatial dependencies and predict slope safety factors.

Step 6: Model Training, Validation, and Comparison

Train the GNN using the Adam optimizer and MSE loss. Compare its performance with other machine learning models such as FNN, RF, SVR and CNN.

Step 7: Model Application and Improvement

Apply the trained GNN to predict slope stability under various geological conditions and improve the model architecture and random field generation as needed.

Illustrative examples

To validate the effectiveness of the developed GNN model in analyzing soil spatial variability, two classic cases are selected for slope stability analysis: an undrained soil slope model and a layered slope model with variations in both cohesion and friction angle. These cases represent common geotechnical conditions, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the GNN model's accuracy and adaptability.

4.1 Dataset configuration and training setup

The experiments are conducted on a high-performance workstation equipped with an Intel Core i7 CPU, NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU, and 128 GB of RAM. This setup ensures efficient handling of intensive model training tasks. Notably, the GNN-based surrogate model demonstrates significant computational efficiency compared to traditional finite element analysis (FEA). For instance, as shown in Table 1, FEA requires approximately 246 hours to process 10,000 samples, while the GNN model can complete training on an equivalent dataset within roughly 13 hours using GPU acceleration. After training, the GNN model achieves highly efficient inference, taking only about 10 minutes to predict slope stability factors for 10,000 samples. This efficiency underscores the GNN model's potential for large-scale and near-real-time slope stability assessments.

The entire dataset, consisting of 10000 FEM-generated samples, was randomly divided into training, validation, and test sets in a ratio of 8:1:1. Specifically, 8000 samples were used for model training, 1000 samples for validation (to tune hyperparameters and prevent over fitting), and the remaining 1000 samples were reserved as an independent test set for final model evaluation. All samples were included in the analysis without exclusion.

In a considerable portion of our experiments, 100 epochs were sufficient for the model to converge and achieve satisfactory prediction accuracy (Fig. 4). Fig. 4 displays the training loss curve for Example 3, which is the most complex case due to its layered structure and parameter cross-correlations. As expected, the simpler cases reached convergence more rapidly; Example 1 and Example 2 achieved stable low loss values within approximately 70 and 85 epochs, respectively. Therefore, setting the training to 100 epochs is a conservative choice that ensures full convergence for all examples. Furthermore, increasing the number of training epochs to 300 ensures that the vast majority of experiments can fully converge, thereby further enhancing the stability and generalization ability of the model. It is also observed that, while different cases exhibit similar convergence speeds, there exist noticeable differences in their final prediction accuracy.

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the numerical results, a mesh convergence analysis was conducted. Models with different numbers of elements (ranging from 50 to 1400) were tested, and the corresponding safety factors were calculated. As shown in Fig. 5, which illustrates the analysis for the most geometrically complex case (Example 3), the safety factor values tend to stabilize when the number of elements exceeds 800, with negligible variations observed for further mesh refinement. Similar analyses for Example 1 and Example 2 demonstrated convergence at approximately 600 and 750 elements, respectively. Based on these results, and to maintain consistency and high precision across all scenarios, a mesh size corresponding to over 2000 elements was selected for all subsequent analyses. This choice ensures high solution accuracy while maintaining reasonable computational efficiency, as the computational cost does not increase significantly beyond this mesh density.

Table 1 Computational time comparison between finite element analysis and GNN model

Method	Computational Time for 10,000 Samples
FEA	246 hours
GNN Model	13 hours (training), 10 minutes (inference)

Fig. 4 Epoch-wise training loss of GNN model

Fig. 5 Safety factor versus number of elements (mesh convergence analysis).

4.2 Hyperparameter configuration and optimization

The performance of the proposed GAT-based surrogate model is highly dependent on the selection of key hyperparameters. In this study, we carefully tuned and selected the hyperparameters based on preliminary experiments and existing literature to achieve optimal model performance. The main hyperparameters and their corresponding values are summarized in Table 2.

The GAT model employs a 3-layer architecture with 8 attention heads per layer and 64 hidden units per layer. This configuration balances model complexity and computational efficiency while ensuring sufficient representational capacity for geotechnical applications. The LeakyReLU activation function with a negative slope of 0.01 is used between layers to prevent the dying ReLU problem, which is particularly important when dealing with

geotechnical data that may contain negative feature values representing stress states or displacement directions.

The spatial connectivity is established using KD-Tree with $k = 10$ nearest neighbors, providing adequate local connectivity while maintaining computational tractability. The SAGE sampling mechanism selects 10 neighbors per node during training, which helps reduce memory requirements while preserving essential spatial relationships in large-scale geotechnical problems. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001, batch size of 32, and a maximum of 100 epochs. The MSE is employed as the loss function, which is well-suited for regression tasks in geotechnical applications. A dropout rate of 0.5 is applied for regularization to prevent overfitting, particularly important given the complex spatial dependencies in geotechnical data. These hyperparameters were selected through systematic grid search and cross-validation on a subset of the training data. While hyper parameters could be individually tuned for each specific case, we opted to use a single, robust configuration for all three examples. This approach ensures a fair and direct comparison of the model's adapt ability to increasing geological complexity, which is a key objective of this study. Preliminary tests indicated that the configuration in Table 2 provided near-optimal performance across all cases, justifying its uniform application.

All experiments were conducted using the hyperparameter configuration detailed in Table 2, ensuring consistency and reproducibility across different geotechnical scenarios.

Table 2 Key hyperparameters of the proposed GAT-based surrogate model

Hyperparameter	Value/Range	Description
Number of GAT layers	3	Number of stacked Graph Attention layers
Number of attention heads	8	Number of attention heads per GAT layer
Hidden units per layer	64	Dimension of hidden features in each layer
Activation function	LeakyReLU	Activation function used between layers
SAGE sampling neighbors	10	Number of neighbors sampled per node (SAGE)
KD-Tree k value	10	Number of nearest neighbors in KD-Tree graph
Learning rate	0.001	Learning rate for the optimizer
Optimizer	Adam	Optimization algorithm
Batch size	32	Number of samples per training batch
Number of epochs	100	Total number of training epochs
Loss function	MSE	Mean squared error used as loss function
Dropout rate	0.3	Dropout rate for regularization

4.3 Example 1: undrained soil slope

4.3.1 Case overview and objectives

The undrained soil slope model is designed to analyze the impact of soil cohesion on slope stability under undrained conditions. This example highlights the ability of the GNN model, equipped with high-fidelity spatial variability simulation, to provide accurate predictions of slope safety factors, particularly emphasizing cohesion's influence under undrained conditions.

4.3.2 Random field generation and finite element computation

In this case, Gaussian Random Fields (GRF) are used to model spatial variability in soil cohesion. Cohesion values follow a log-normal distribution with a mean of 23 kPa and a coefficient of variation of 0.3. Additional soil properties include an elastic modulus E of 100 MPa, Poisson's ratio ν of 0.3, and unit weight γ of 20 kN/m³. Horizontal and vertical spatial correlation distances are set to 25 m and 2.5 m, respectively, ensuring that the spatial distribution of soil cohesion aligns with realistic undrained slope conditions [5]. Fig. 6 delineates the computational mesh configuration employing triangular elements with an average edge length of 0.4 m, and intuitively illustrates the process of mesh partitioning and neighbor selection, providing a clear visualization of how the neighborhood is constructed.

Before proceeding with surrogate modeling and reliability analysis, the numerical model for Example 1 was validated. Using the mean values of the soil parameters, the FS was calculated as 1.366, which is exactly consistent with the value reported in Ding et al. [5]. This

agreement confirms that the finite element model and boundary conditions adopted in this study are accurate and reliable for this benchmark case.

The GRF-generated cohesion values are processed through Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion, which reduces dimensionality while preserving essential spatial correlations. A total of 1000 expansion terms were used to balance computational efficiency and spatial fidelity, maintaining a high level of detail in soil variability representation. Fig. 7 shows the spatial distribution of soil cohesion across the slope, highlighting the spatial variability incorporated in this case.

Using Python, 10000 sets of soil parameters are generated and imported into OptumG2 finite element software for iterative calculation of slope's safety factors. The finite element model grid comprises 2000 triangular elements, with boundary conditions fixed at the base and constrained horizontally at the lateral sides. Fig. 8 displays the resulting strain contour map, showing both stable and unstable conditions with safety factors (FS) of 1.396 and 0.9441, respectively, which are used as label data for GNN model training and validation.

In this example, the failure probability was estimated as 9.30 %, corresponding to a reliability index of $\beta = 1.32$. The convergence of these indicators was verified by increasing the number of samples, and the results remained stable, confirming the robustness and reliability of the analysis.

It should be noted that the finite element mesh size and model boundary conditions may influence the computed safety factor and the shape of the critical sliding surface, as discussed in Wu et al., [21]. In this study, the numerical settings were kept the same as those in the benchmark cases to ensure direct comparison. However, in practical applications,

extending the model boundary or refining the mesh may result in deeper or different failure mechanisms, especially when the critical slip surface approaches the model bottom (see Fig. 8). Future studies may systematically investigate the effect of numerical modeling parameters on the robustness and accuracy of surrogate models.

Fig. 6 Structure topology schematic (Example 1).

Fig. 7 One typical realization of soil cohesion distribution in the undrained slope model (Example 1).

Fig. 8 Strain contour map showing slope stability with safety factor (FS=1.396, left; FS=0.944, right) (Example 1).

4.3.3 Graph structure construction and GNN model configuration

Each soil element's spatial position and cohesion characteristics are structured into a graph representation, where nodes represent soil units, and edges are formed with each node's 10 nearest neighbors. The KD-Tree method is used to efficiently establish these adjacency relationships, reducing memory usage while retaining essential spatial and mechanical dependencies. Edge weights are assigned based on the Euclidean distance between nodes, preserving key spatial relationships. The GNN model is based on a GAT architecture with a three-layer structure and multi-head attention mechanisms. This setup allows the model to capture complex inter-node interactions, dynamically adjusting the attention weights for each neighboring node. The final graph-level features are generated through global pooling, providing a comprehensive representation of the slope's stability conditions.

4.3.4 Model training, validation, and results

To rigorously evaluate the model's generalization capability, the performance metrics reported here are exclusively derived from the independent test set, which the model has

not previously seen during training or hyperparameter tuning. After training, the GNN model is compared with baseline machine learning models, including FNN, RF, (SVR, and CNNs. Table 3 presents the predictive performance metrics (R^2 , MSE, and MAE) for each model. The GNN outperforms the others, achieving the highest R^2 and lowest MSE and MAE, indicating superior accuracy in minimizing prediction errors. The CNN also shows competitive results, but is still slightly inferior to the GNN, especially as the complexity of the problem increases. Additionally, paired t-tests (shown in Fig. 9) reveal statistically significant differences between GNN and the other models, reinforcing its predictive advantage. It is important to emphasize that all reported performance metrics (e.g., in Tables 3, 5, and 7) are based on the independent test set. This ensures that the evaluation reflects the model's generalization capability to unseen data.

To further investigate the influence of training sample size on model performance, we conducted a convergence study by training the model with different numbers of training samples (1000; 2000; 4000; 6000; and 8000), while keeping the validation and test sets unchanged. The results show that the prediction accuracy increases rapidly as the training sample size grows, and becomes nearly stable when the sample size reaches around 2000, with only marginal improvements observed beyond this point. When the training set exceeds 6000 samples, no significant improvement in accuracy is observed. It should also be noted that increasing the sample size substantially raises memory usage and computational cost. Therefore, the choice of 10,000 samples in this study represents a balanced decision between model accuracy and computational efficiency.

Model performance is further illustrated in Fig. 10, which includes scatter plots of predicted vs. true safety factors, as well as residual distributions for each model. The GNN model shows the closest alignment with the true values, as evidenced by a tight clustering along the diagonal line, and a more centralized residual distribution, which further highlights its precision in predicting slope stability.

These results confirm that the GNN model, by capturing spatial variability in soil cohesion, provides a reliable prediction of slope stability factors under undrained conditions. The GNN’s dynamic attention mechanism enables it to prioritize critical spatial relationships, making it particularly effective in real-world applications requiring high accuracy in heterogeneous soil conditions.

This example provides a baseline using core features, and the next example, Example 2, will apply the same methods with the addition of an extra soil parameter, enhancing the analysis for more complex slope conditions.

Table 3 Predictive performance metrics (R^2 , MSE, MAE) for GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN models in slope stability prediction (Example 1).

Model	R^2	MSE	MAE
GNN	0.9938	0.000224	0.01241
FNN	0.9866	0.000536	0.01850
Random Forest	0.9851	0.000594	0.01916
SVR	0.9685	0.001258	0.02919
CNN	0.9756	0.001015	0.02628

Fig. 9 Paired t-test Results for Model Comparison (GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN) in Predicting Slope Stability (Example 1)

Fig. 10 Predicted vs. True Safety Factors and Residual Distributions for GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN Models (Example 1)

4.4 Example 2: congress street cut in Chicago

4.4.1 Case Overview and Objectives

The layered slope model is designed to examine the stability of a slope composed of four distinct soil layers, each with varying cohesion and friction angle [29]. This example

serves to validate the GNN model's adaptability and accuracy under more complex conditions than the undrained soil slope in Example 1. Specifically, the layered structure adds complexity by introducing discontinuities in soil properties, which challenge the model's ability to capture interactions between different material zones.

4.4.2 Random field generation and finite element computation

In this case, the soil properties vary significantly across different layers, including Sand, Clay1, Clay2, and Clay3. Table 4 outlines the key parameters for each layer, including unit weight, cohesion, and angle of internal friction. Each property is represented with its mean, coefficient of variation (COV), and distribution type (e.g., lognormal). For instance, the uppermost sand layer has a unit weight of 21 kN/m^3 , zero cohesion, and an internal friction angle of 30° , while the underlying clay layers exhibit higher cohesion values and lower friction angles, introducing notable heterogeneity into the slope's stability profile. Horizontal and vertical spatial correlation distances are set to 20 m and 6 m. The parameter values and statistical properties used for the numerical simulation in this case are summarized in Table 4 [29,30].

For Example 2, the Congress street cut in Chicago example, the numerical model was validated by computing the safety factor based on the mean values of the soil properties. The obtained safety factor is 1.565, which is identical to the reference value reported by Jiang and Huang [29]. This validation ensures the correctness of the model setup and provides a solid basis for the subsequent surrogate modeling.

Table 4 Soil layer parameters for the layered slope model in Example 2.

Slope layers		Sand	Clay1	Clay2	Clay3
Unit weight, γ (KN/m ³)		21	19.5	19.5	20
Cohesion, c (kPa)	Mean	0	55	43	56
	COV	\	0.37	0.19	0.2
	Distribution	\	Lognormal	Lognormal	Lognormal
Angle of internal friction, ϕ (°)	Mean	30	5	7	15
	COV	\	0.2	0.21	0.24
	Distribution	\	Lognormal	Lognormal	Lognormal

The random field generation method in this example follows the process described in Section 4.1. Specific adjustments include the addition of friction angle as a spatially variable parameter. Table 4 summarizes the log-normal distribution characteristics of cohesion and friction angle in the layered slope model. This added complexity introduces heterogeneity into the slope, simulating real-world geotechnical engineering challenges. As shown in Fig. 6, the distributions of cohesion and friction angle for each layer illustrate the complex spatial variability within the slope. The upper layer, characterized by higher variability in cohesion (COV=0.25), demonstrates a more irregular pattern, while the lower layer shows comparatively uniform distributions due to its lower variability (COV=0.10). These differences highlight the influence of material heterogeneity on potential failure mechanisms, particularly at the layer interface. Fig. 11 delineates the computational mesh configuration with an average edge length of 0.6 m, and intuitively illustrates the process of

mesh partitioning and neighbor selection, providing a clear visualization of how the neighborhood is constructed.

Using these spatially variable parameters, 10,000 parameter sets are generated and imported into OptumG2 finite element software for slope stability analysis. The finite element model incorporates boundary conditions and a mesh of 3,000 triangular elements to handle the complexity of the layered structure. The results of the finite element analysis are shown in Fig. 12, highlighting the strain contour maps under different safety factors (FS=1.642 for a stable slope and FS=1.49 for a near-critical slope condition). In this example, the failure probability was estimated as 1.46%, corresponding to a reliability index of $\beta = 2.17$. The convergence of these indicators was verified by increasing the number of samples, and the results remained stable, confirming the robustness and reliability of the analysis.

In Fig. 12, high strain concentrations are observed at the interface between the two soil layers, particularly in regions where the upper layer exhibits greater variability in cohesion. This localized strain distribution suggests that the layer interface serves as a critical failure zone due to the contrasting material properties between the upper and lower layers. As the FS decreases from 1.642 to 1.49, the strain concentration becomes more pronounced, indicating the progressive development of a slip surface that initiates near the layer boundary and propagates through the weaker upper layer.

These findings emphasize the importance of accounting for layered material heterogeneity in slope stability analysis. The ability to model spatial variability and interface behavior is crucial for accurately predicting the failure surface and associated safety factors. The results in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 validate the relevance of incorporating advanced random

field techniques and finite element modeling in capturing the complexities of real-world geotechnical scenarios.

Fig. 11 Structure topology schematic (Example 2).

Fig. 12 Cohesion and friction angle distributions in the layered slope model (Example 2).

Fig. 13 Strain Contour Map Showing Slope Stability with Safety Factor (FS=1.574, left; FS=1.490, right) (Example 2)

4.4.3 Graph structure construction and GNN model configuration

The graph structure construction and GNN model configuration follow the methodology described in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2. Each node represents an element in the finite element mesh, with features including cohesion and friction angle values, as well as geometric properties. For this layered slope model, an additional feature indicating the layer to which each node belongs is introduced. Furthermore, edges at the boundaries between layers are assigned adjusted weights to capture the discontinuity effects. The GNN architecture remains a three-layer GAT with multi-head attention.

4.4.4 Model Training, Validation, and Results

Training and optimization follow similar steps to Example 1, with minor adjustments in hyperparameters to account for the increased heterogeneity in the layered slope. The GNN model's performance is compared to baseline models. As shown in Table 5, the GNN achieves the highest R^2 and the lowest MSE and MAE, outperforming the other models. These results underscore the GNN's adaptability in complex environments.

Table 5 Predictive performance metrics (R^2 , MSE, MAE) for GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN models in layered slope (Example 2).

Model	R^2	MSE	MAE
GNN	0.9928	0.000230	0.01282
FNN	0.9839	0.000514	0.01694
Random Forest	0.9828	0.000550	0.01663
SVR	0.8805	0.003815	0.05113
CNN	0.9482	0.001654	0.03090

The statistical significance of the differences between models is verified through paired t-tests, as displayed in Fig. 14. The p-values indicate that the GNN outperforms other models with high statistical confidence, especially in handling the layered slope's complexity.

Fig. 14 Paired t-test results for model comparison (GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN) in predicting slope stability (Example 2).

Fig. 15 Predicted vs. True Safety Factors and Residual Distributions for GNN, FNN, RF, and SVR Models in Layered Slope (Example 2)

Fig. 15 presents scatter plots and residual distributions for each model. As seen, the GNN model's predictions align closely with the true safety factors despite the layered

structure's complexity, with residuals concentrated near zero, highlighting the model's precision.

The layered slope results emphasize the GNN's adaptability to complex geotechnical conditions. Compared to the undrained slope in Example 1, the layered slope introduces additional challenges due to discontinuities in material properties. However, as seen in Table 5 and Fig. 14, the GNN consistently outperforms other models, demonstrating its robustness in diverse soil conditions. In both cases, Fig. 15 highlights the GNN's superior alignment with true values compared to traditional models, emphasizing its strength in environments with significant spatial variability.

This example reaffirms that the GNN model, with its spatial attention mechanism and GraphSAGE sampling, effectively adapts to complex slope conditions and offers advantages in real-world applications requiring accuracy across varied geotechnical environments.

4.5 Example 3: two-layered slope with correlated soil properties

4.5.1 Case overview and objectives

This case examines a two-layered slope model designed to evaluate the influence of cross-correlations between cohesion (c) and internal friction angle (φ) on slope reliability. Unlike the previous examples, this case incorporates parameter correlations to reflect the realistic interactions between soil properties, adding complexity to the spatial variability analysis. The upper layer is characterized by higher variability in cohesion compared to the lower layer, creating a critical zone where potential failures are most likely to initiate. The primary objectives of this case are to assess how parameter correlations influence the spatial

distributions of key soil properties and their effects on failure mechanisms, to explore the reliability of the slope by analyzing the failure probability (P_f) under probabilistic conditions, and to validate the adaptability of the GNN model in capturing complex interdependencies and variability introduced by cross-correlations in multi-layered slopes. Such cases are frequently encountered in engineering practices, especially for slopes with stratified soil layers underlain by cohesive materials, where parameter correlations significantly affect failure probability.

In this study, the correlation between c and φ is expressed through a cross-correlation coefficient (ρ), which is integrated into the random field generation process. The spatial variability of each parameter is modeled using Gaussian Random Fields (GRF), with Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion applied to reduce dimensionality while preserving spatial correlations. These random fields are then incorporated into the finite element analysis (FEA) framework to evaluate the slope's stability, including the identification of critical slip surfaces and zones of potential failure. This example introduces cross-correlated variability into slope reliability analysis, adding a new dimension to the GNN model's capability to handle complex soil-structure interactions in geotechnical engineering.

4.5.2 Random field generation and finite element computation

In this example, the random field generation method follows the approach outlined in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2, with specific modifications to incorporate cross-correlations between cohesion (c) and internal friction angle (φ). The spatial variability of these soil properties is modeled using Gaussian Random Fields (GRF) with isotropic covariance functions, and the cross-correlation between parameters is represented by a correlation

coefficient (ρ). This correlation introduces interdependencies between c and φ , reflecting their coupled behavior in geotechnical conditions. The covariance matrix for the random field is adjusted to include this correlation, ensuring that the generated distributions capture realistic soil property interactions. The covariance function is expressed as:

$$\text{Cov}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \sigma_i \sigma_j \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|}{\delta}\right) \cdot \rho_{ij} \quad (9)$$

where σ_i and σ_j are the standard deviations of c and φ , δ is the scale of fluctuation, $\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|$ represents the spatial distance between two points, and ρ_{ij} is the correlation coefficient between the parameters at locations \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j . This modification allows the random field to simulate the coupled spatial variability of soil properties effectively.

The two-layered slope is defined with distinct properties for the upper and lower layers. The upper layer exhibits higher variability in c and φ , while the lower layer is relatively stable, as summarized in Table 6 [31]. A total of 10,000 realizations of the random field are generated using Monte Carlo simulations, with the random fields discretized through Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion to reduce computational complexity while preserving essential spatial correlations. The first 100 KL terms are retained, balancing efficiency and fidelity in the representation of spatial variability.

The numerical model for Case 3 was similarly validated. By employing the mean values of the soil parameters, the calculated safety factor is 1.592, matching exactly with the value in Cho [31]. This result confirms the validity and reliability of the numerical implementation for this layered slope example.

Table 6 Soil layer parameters for the layered slope model in Example 3.

Layer	Property	Mean value	Coefficient of Variation (COV)	Correlation Coefficient (ρ)
Upper Layer	Unit weight, γ (KN/m ³)	18	0.05	
	Cohesion, c (kPa)	38.31	0.2	-0.7
	Friction, ϕ (°)	0.0	-	
Lower Layer	Unit weight, γ (KN/m ³)	18	0.05	-0.5
	Cohesion, c (kPa)	23.94	0.2	
	Friction, ϕ (°)	12	0.1	

In this example, the random field generation method follows the approach outlined in Section 4.3, with specific modifications to incorporate cross-correlations between cohesion (c) and internal friction angle (ϕ). The spatial variability of these soil properties is modeled using Gaussian Random Fields (GRF) with isotropic covariance functions, and the cross-correlation between parameters is represented by a correlation coefficient (ρ). This correlation introduces interdependencies between c and ϕ , reflecting their coupled behavior in realistic geotechnical conditions. Fig. 18 illustrates the spatial distributions of cohesion and friction angle for the two-layered slope, generated using GRF and parameterized based on the statistical characteristics summarized in Table 6. These fields highlight the heterogeneity introduced by cross-correlations, particularly in the upper layer, where variability is most significant. Fig. 17 delineates the computational mesh configuration with an average edge length of 0.6 m, and intuitively illustrates the process of mesh partitioning and neighbor selection, providing a clear visualization of how the neighborhood is constructed.

The random fields for c and φ are discretized using Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion, retaining the first 100 terms to ensure computational efficiency while preserving spatial correlations. A total of 10,000 realizations are generated and imported into the OptumG2 finite element software for slope stability analysis. The finite element model employs a triangular mesh with 3,500 elements to resolve the complexity of the two-layered structure. Boundary conditions are applied with fixed constraints at the base and lateral edges. The Strength Reduction Method (SSR) is used to evaluate the safety factor (FS) by iteratively reducing soil strength parameters until failure occurs.

Fig. 19 shows the strain contour maps obtained from the finite element analysis under two distinct safety factors (FS=1.637 for a stable slope, and FS = 1.196 for a near-critical state). These results demonstrate the progression of failure mechanisms and the concentration of strains at the interface between the two layers, where cross-correlation effects significantly influence the failure surface's geometry. The incorporation of parameter correlations into the random fields enables the model to capture more realistic slip surface patterns and enhances the understanding of coupled soil-structure interactions.

Based on the 10,000 FEA samples, the failure probability for this example was estimated to be 0.64 % (reliability index $\beta = 2.48$). It is important to note that for this number of samples, the coefficient of variation of the failure probability (COV_Pf) is approximately 12.5 %, which is slightly above the commonly accepted threshold of 10 % for convergence. This indicates that 10,000 direct FEA simulations, while computationally demanding, may still be insufficient for achieving a fully converged reliability estimate for this low-probability problem.

However, this limitation of direct Monte Carlo simulation underscores the significant value of our proposed GNN surrogate model. As will be demonstrated in Section 4.5.4, the trained GNN model can generate a much larger sample set (e.g., over 100,000 samples) in minutes. This allows for a rigorous convergence analysis that would be computationally prohibitive with traditional FEA. For instance, by increasing the sample size to 30,000 using the GNN, the COV_Pf reduces to approximately 7.2 %, ensuring a stable and reliable estimate of the failure probability. This capability highlights the critical role of efficient surrogate models in practical reliability analysis, especially for problems involving rare failure events.

Further reinforcing the practical utility of the GNN model, we revisited the convergence issue of the failure probability Pf for Example 3. By leveraging the high computational efficiency of the trained GNN model, we were able to perform a comprehensive convergence study with up to 30,000 samples, a task infeasible with direct FEA. As shown in Fig. 16, the predicted Pf stabilizes as the number of samples increases, confirming that the estimate of 0.64 % is robust. This analysis not only validates the reliability estimate but also demonstrates the GNN's capability to enable rigorous probabilistic assessments that are beyond the reach of conventional simulation methods.

By integrating correlated variability and conducting finite element computations, this case provides critical insights into the influence of interdependent soil properties on slope reliability, offering a valuable dataset for GNN model validation and training.

Fig. 16 Convergence study of failure probability (Pf) for Example 3 using the GNN surrogate model.

Fig. 17 Structure Topology Schematic (Example 3)

Fig. 18 Cohesion and Friction Angle Distributions in the Layered Slope Model (Example 3)

Fig. 19 Strain Contour Map Showing Slope Stability with Safety Factor (FS=1.637, left; FS=1.196, right) (Example 3)

4.5.3 Graph structure construction and GNN model configuration

The graph structure construction and GNN model configuration are consistent with the approach described in Section 4.1. To accommodate the parameter correlations introduced in this example, the node features are augmented to include cross-correlation coefficients (cohesion (c) and friction angle (φ)). This additional feature enables the GNN to better capture the coupled effects of these parameters during training. The overall architecture and hyperparameters of the GNN remain unchanged.

4.5.4 Model Training, Validation, and Results

The results for the two-layered slope with correlated soil properties provide critical insights into the performance of different models in predicting slope stability under complex

geotechnical conditions. The inclusion of parameter correlations and a multi-layered structure distinguishes this case from Examples 1 and 2, introducing additional challenges for modeling and prediction.

Table 7 clearly demonstrates the superior performance of the GNN model in predicting safety factors under complex geotechnical conditions. With an R^2 value of 0.9865, an MSE of 0.000191, and an MAE of 0.01093, the GNN consistently outperformed FNN, RF, SVR and CNN. The large performance gap is particularly evident in the MSE metric, where GNN achieved a 76% reduction compared to RF and an 80% reduction compared to SVR, highlighting its ability to handle complex spatial variability and parameter correlations.

Table 7 Predictive performance metrics (R^2 , MSE, MAE) for GNN, FNN, random forest, and SVR models in layered slope (Example 3).

Model	R^2	MSE	MAE
GNN	0.9865	0.000191	0.01093
FNN	0.9415	0.000823	0.02252
Random Forest	0.9121	0.001244	0.02864
SVR	0.9341	0.000933	0.02404
CNN	0.9467	0.000793	0.02363

Fig. 20 further reinforces the statistical significance of these differences through paired t-tests. The comparisons show statistically significant differences between GNN and the other models, with p-values less than 10^{-5} in all cases. Specifically, the GNN significantly outperformed FNN (2.99×10^{-23}), RF (1.04×10^{-24}), SVR (6.01×10^{-35}), and CNN ($1.93 \times$

10^{-23}), demonstrating its robustness in this challenging scenario. These results are based on log-transformed data, which helped mitigate the effects of extreme values and outliers, ensuring a more stable comparison across models. The log transformation of p-values emphasizes the significant differences between the models, particularly where the GNN shows substantial improvement. These findings underscore the GNN's ability to leverage spatial dependencies and hierarchical feature representations, which are crucial for making accurate slope stability predictions under complex, real-world conditions.

In contrast, the performance of traditional machine learning models like RF and SVR suffered due to their inability to capture spatial and structural correlations. RF, while robust for simpler datasets, is limited by its reliance on non-spatial decision trees that cannot model interactions between correlated features like cohesion (c) and friction angle (ϕ). Similarly, SVR, which excels in low-dimensional problems, struggles to generalize effectively in high-dimensional, graph-structured data.

Fig. 20 Paired t-test Results for Model Comparison (GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN) in Predicting Slope Stability (Example 3)

Fig. 21 Predicted vs. True Safety Factors and Residual Distributions for GNN, FNN, RF, SVR and CNN Models in Layered Slope (Example 3)

Fig. 21 illustrates the relationship between predicted and true safety factors across the models. The GNN predictions align closely with the true values, as indicated by the clustering of points along the diagonal line. In contrast, the predictions from FNN, RF, SVR and CNN exhibit larger deviations, particularly for lower safety factor values. The residual distributions, shown in the inset boxplot, further emphasize the GNN's accuracy, with the smallest residual variance among all models. This concentrated residual distribution highlights the GNN's robustness in capturing complex spatial variability and parameter interactions, making it particularly suitable for probabilistic slope stability analysis. It is worth noting that the GNN model demonstrates superior predictive performance in the tail region of the safety factor distribution, which is crucial for accurate failure probability

estimation. This advantage is particularly evident when compared with other surrogate models.

Compared to Examples 1 and 2, the introduction of parameter correlations (ρ) and the two-layered slope structure in this case created additional modeling challenges. In Example 1, the focus was on a homogeneous slope with no parameter correlations, resulting in relatively straightforward spatial variability patterns. Example 2 introduced heterogeneity through a layered slope model but did not account for parameter correlations, which simplified the feature learning process. However, in this example, the inclusion of cross-correlations (ρ) between cohesion (c) and internal friction angle (φ) significantly increased the complexity of the failure mechanisms, as shown by the strain localization at the interface between layers in Fig. 19. This added complexity required the GNN to leverage its graph-based representation and multi-layer attention mechanisms to accurately capture these interactions, highlighting its adaptability to diverse geotechnical scenarios.

Despite its superior performance, the GNN exhibited a slight reduction in predictive accuracy compared to the results in Examples 1 and 2. As shown in Table 7, the GNN's residual variance increased marginally in this case, which may be attributed to the interplay between correlated parameters (c and φ). The presence of parameter correlations appears to obscure individual feature contributions, reducing the model's ability to fully exploit its graph-based architecture for disentangling distinct patterns. This finding is consistent with the observed residual spread in Fig. 20, where the GNN maintains its overall accuracy but struggles slightly to generalize as effectively as in the previous examples.

These results underscore the importance of incorporating parameter correlations in probabilistic slope stability analysis. Neglecting these correlations, as observed in the weaker performance of FNN, RF, SVR and CNN, can lead to less accurate predictions and potential underestimation of failure risks. RF, for instance, relies on non-spatial decision trees that fail to capture the interdependencies between c and φ , while SVR struggles to generalize effectively in high-dimensional, graph-structured data. In contrast, the GNN's ability to dynamically learn hierarchical feature interactions allows it to consistently outperform traditional methods.

The broader implications of these findings suggest that incorporating advanced feature disentanglement techniques or introducing domain-specific priors into the GNN framework may help address the challenges posed by cross-correlations. Future research could explore adjustments to the graph construction process, such as encoding correlation information directly into edge weights or using separate subgraphs for each parameter, to further improve model performance. Additionally, integrating more sophisticated attention mechanisms or leveraging graph-based regularization techniques could enhance the GNN's ability to adapt to even more complex geotechnical scenarios.

Conclusion

This study presents a novel graph neural network (GNN)-based surrogate modeling framework for efficient slope stability analysis, which effectively addresses the challenges of spatial variability in geotechnical engineering. The primary finding is that the proposed GNN model demonstrates superior performance and computational efficiency compared to conventional machine learning approaches, including FNN, RF, SVR, and CNN, across three

distinct benchmark cases. The results quantitatively validate the GNN's capabilities. The model consistently achieved the highest predictive accuracy with R^2 values exceeding 0.986, MSE values below 0.0003, and MAE values under 0.013 in all scenarios. Most significantly, the framework reduced computational time from 246 hours required by traditional FEA to approximately 13 hours for training and a mere 10 minutes for inference on 10,000 samples, marking an efficiency improvement of over 95 %. This dramatic reduction makes large-scale Monte Carlo simulations and the analysis of low-probability failure events practically feasible.

Furthermore, the progressive complexity of the three case studies revealed the GNN's particular strengths. The model not only performed well in a single-parameter spatial variability context (Example 1) but also showed exceptional adaptability to more complex geological conditions, such as multi-layered structures (Example 2) and layered slopes with cross-correlated soil properties (Example 3). Unlike traditional methods that struggle with irregular spatial data, the GNN's graph-based representation effectively captured these intricate physical interactions, maintaining high accuracy where other models faltered. While this framework demonstrates significant advantages, its performance is inherently dependent on the quality and representativeness of the training data, and its current scope is limited to static stability analysis. Future research should prioritize the integration of physics-informed constraints to enhance model interpretability, as well as the extension of the framework to dynamic loading conditions such as seismic and hydrological effects. Developing transfer learning strategies would also be crucial for improving model generalizability across diverse geological contexts, further solidifying the GNN's potential as a powerful and transformative tool in computational geotechnics.

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